

The geological excursions of the Alpine School of Morbegno: the valley floor of the Valtellina

Enrico Cameron

IC2 Damiani of Morbegno– Alpine School Program (Italy, Sondrio Province) and Italian Geological Society – Section of Geoethics and Geological Culture

1. The Alpine School of Morbegno

Valtellina is an Alpine geographical region in northern Lombardy that corresponds—except for a small portion—to the drainage basin of the Adda River upstream of Lake Como. Together with Valchiavenna, it forms the territory of the Province of Sondrio (**Fig. 1**).

Fig. 1 – The Province of Sondrio and the Valtellina in the context of Northern Italy

Morbegno is the main urban center of the Lower Valtellina and is home to the Istituto Comprensivo 2 Damiani, which in 2017 joined the Interreg Alpine Space – YOUrALPS project, aimed at

developing a new school model focused on the environmental and socio-economic processes of the Alps. In 2020, after three years of intensive work on the educational model, the lower secondary school of the Institute obtained the European Alpine School certification, officially establishing a dedicated program. The main goal is to reconnect students with their local area, raising awareness of the features, resources, and opportunities of the mountain environment.

The Alpine School's educational model organically integrates the mountains into the learning pathway, using an interdisciplinary approach across various subjects. A key aspect is also the involvement of groups such as the Italian Alpine Club (CAI) and the Alpine Rescue Service, as well as local associations and community organizations. The teaching approach combines the use of technology with hands-on field experiences, allowing students to apply theoretical knowledge through direct observation and analysis of the mountain environment.

Geology and geomorphology naturally play a significant role within the Alpine School, and outdoor education is a fundamental component of the program. The goal is not only learning, but also to foster a positive early connection between young students and the Geosciences—an aim whose importance has been emphasized multiple times, particularly in light of the declining appeal of these disciplines (see, for example, the contribution by Hollis et al. in *Geoethics For the Future: Facing Global Challenges*, and the works of the working group “Earth Sciences in Italy Today” of the Italian Geological Society).

The School organizes several geology- and geomorphology-themed field trips, which also include visits to various geosites in the Province of Sondrio—places, areas, or territories where a geological or geomorphological interest relevant to conservation can be identified (Regione Lombardia and IREALP, 2008; Wimbledon, 1996).

Among the excursions, particularly noteworthy are the educational visit to the Marmite dei Giganti Park, a geosite in Val Chiavenna, and the visit to the Antonio Sella Glaciological Trail, a geosite in Val Ventina (Servizio Glaciologico Lombardo, 2009). The latter includes activities developed in collaboration with the “A. Desio” Department of Earth Sciences at the University of Milan. Some of

these activities, and their positive impact on student learning, have been the subject of a thesis and a poster presented at the joint congress of the Italian Society of Mineralogy and Petrology, the Italian Geological Society, the Italian Geochemical Society, and the Italian Association of Volcanology, held in Potenza in 2023 (Pelfini et al., 2023).

Another excursion organized by the Alpine School focuses on the observation of significant landslide phenomena and their effects, along a route that runs through the Valtellina valley floor. This is the itinerary described in the present contribution, selected for four main reasons.

First, it crosses areas of particular geological and geomorphological interest, including four additional geosites in the Province of Sondrio. Second, the observed phenomena help raise awareness of key geomorphological processes that have recently affected—and may again affect—the Valtellina valley floor, an area that hosts much of the Province of Sondrio's population, but which is not always associated—even by residents—with the mountain environment and its dynamics.

Third, the excursion is potentially accessible to everyone, with the possibility of introducing a variant described in Section 4. Finally, the route extends for nearly 80 kilometers from Lower to Upper Valtellina, allowing participants to appreciate landscape changes along the valley and to observe sites of historical, artistic, architectural, and scenic importance.

2. A geological-geomorphological excursion along the Valtellina valley floor

2.1 The geological-geomorphological context

The lithosphere, which includes the Earth's crust, is the outermost and most rigid layer of our planet, and it is divided into several sections known as tectonic plates, which are in relative motion with respect to one another. The Alpine chain, as is well known, is the result of the convergence and subsequent collision between the African and Eurasian plates, involving the subduction of the former Ligurian–Piedmont Ocean, whose lithosphere has largely sunk beneath the African plate. This process began approximately 130 million years ago, culminated around 50 million years ago, and is still ongoing today.

As a result of this collision, massive rock bodies (the so-called thrust sheets or nappes) were displaced one over another toward the north, in some cases over distances of hundreds of kilometers. Within the Alpine arc, from north to south, three main tectonic domains are recognized: the Helvetic Domain, the Penninic Domain, and the Austroalpine Domain, consisting of rocks originating respectively from the Eurasian plate, from part of the ancient oceanic lithosphere, and from the African plate. Further south lies the Southalpine Domain, made up of rocks from the African plate that were deformed after the main collision event. This domain is separated from the others by a fault system extending over 700 kilometers, known as the Periadriatic Lineament or Insubric Line (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 – Simplified diagram of the Alpine nappes (modified from Wikimedia Commons: *Falde Alpine.svg*). The rocks of the Gonfolite originate from sediments deposited along the southern margin of the Alpine chain in a marine environment by currents rich in suspended detrital material. The rocks of the Molasse derive from sediments deposited in basins parallel to the margin of the uplifting Alpine chain and sourced from that same rising chain. The foreland, finally, is the region in front of a mountain range that is little or not at all deformed

The rocks exposed in Valtellina mainly belong to the Austroalpine and Southalpine domains, although the Penninic domain is also well represented—particularly in the Valmalenco area, which also includes the previously mentioned Val Ventina. Noteworthy as well is the presence of rocks

formed by the deep cooling of large magmatic bodies, such as the *ghiandone* (a type of coarse-grained granite), which forms the slopes of Val Masino.

The Insubric Line crosses much of Valtellina from east to west and appears to influence the east–west orientation of the central and lower parts of the valley. In addition to the Insubric Line, numerous faults of local or regional importance and other discontinuities affect the rock masses, which are therefore extensively fractured.

The current landforms of the main valley and its many lateral valleys are shaped primarily by erosional and depositional processes driven both by glaciers (especially those from the Pleistocene, which developed within a pre-existing valley and drainage system) and by surface water and present-day streams. Landslide phenomena have also produced significant landforms in the Valtellina area, some of which are described in this report. Several of these processes—and their associated landforms—will be examined in greater detail during the excursion presentation.

Faults and other discontinuities play a key role in landscape development, as they represent zones of weakness in the rock masses that are more easily attacked by weathering and erosional agents. Moreover, they promote and influence the occurrence and evolution of landslides and other slope instability phenomena.

2.2 The route

2.2.1 First Stop: the Tartano Stream fan and the Pizzo della Pruna landslide

At the mouths of valleys, the slope and lateral confinement of watercourses decrease, leading to a corresponding reduction in the stream's transport capacity. As a result, the current progressively deposits the sediments it carries. These materials, accumulating in the riverbed, promote the shifting of the watercourse alternately in one direction or another, and over time, the detrital deposits form fan-shaped landforms—known as alluvial fans—with their apexes pointing toward the valley outlets. However, the formation of a fan can be influenced, to varying or even dominant degrees, by debris flows—which will be discussed shortly—or by landslides. For this reason, Derbyshire and Owen

(1990) suggest using the more neutral term *sedimentary fans*, which avoids the word “alluvial,” as various processes may contribute to the genesis of these landforms. In this contribution, we will simply use the term *fan*. Most Valtellina settlements (including Morbegno) are built on fans of varying sizes that formed after the last glaciation, offering a relatively protected environment compared to the Adda valley floor, which was subject to frequent flooding.

Val Tartano is a lateral valley of Valtellina, traversed by the Tartano Stream (*torrente Tartano*), located on the left bank of the Adda River, within the Orobic Alps and the Southalpine Domain. It contains extensive areas covered by detrital mantles, which supply large quantities of material potentially transportable by the Tartano Stream (Francani, 2017). The broad fan built by this stream spreads into the valley floor, pushing the Adda River toward the opposite (Rhaetian) side, at the foot of the small hill of Colmen di Dazio (Fig. 3). Due to its active dynamics and associated hazards, this area is classified as non-buildable and constitutes the first geosite visited on the excursion.

Fig. 3 – The Tartano fan and the surrounding area (see main text): 1) Adda River, 2) Tartano fan, 3) Mouth of Val Tartano, 4) Fan of the Roncaiola, Malasca, and Ranciga streams with the town of Talamona, 5) Segment of the former SS38 road route, 6) Town of Desco, 7) Traces of a small recent rockfall, 8) Colmen di Dazio; the red star in the inset at the top left shows the location of the area within the Province of Sondrio

From the fan, near the end of Val Tartano and on the left bank of the stream, a large paleo-rockslide is clearly visible. It detached from the eastern slope of a relief known as Pizzo della Pruna (Photo 1) and slipped downhill for over 100 meters (Francani, 2017; Agostoni et al., 1997). The detachment of the landslide was facilitated by the presence of fault and fracture systems, which represent zones of low strength within the rock masses and also allow easier water infiltration, further reducing the overall resistance.

Photo 1 – The mouth of Val Tartano with the Pruna landslide, seen from the Tartano Stream fan – 1) landslide deposit; 2) Pizzo della Pruna; 3) some discontinuities; 4) the slope above Talamona, affected by discontinuities and rockfalls

The landslide deposit is between 40 and 80 meters thick and shows evidence of superficial remobilization near its base, caused by the erosive action of the Tartano Stream. In 1993, following a period of intense and prolonged rainfall, the landslide underwent a general reactivation, evidenced by the opening of a fracture several hundred meters long in its upper portion (Agostoni et al., 1997). In 2001 and 2002, again during particularly intense weather events, significant deformations of the landslide body were recorded (Francani, 2017).

The debris transported by the stream is now almost entirely retained by a dam (the Colombera Dam) built just upstream of the landslide deposit. As a result, the landslide now constitutes the nearly exclusive source of the materials that form the Tartano fan, and large volumes of this material have been removed since 2002 (Francani, 2017).

One can distinguish—and even walk across—the braided channels that are only occasionally occupied by the stream. However, the fan is usually dry, since the typical discharges released by the dam fully infiltrate due to the high permeability of the deposits. On the surface, one mostly sees boulders and pebbles smoothed by collisions—both with each other and with the streambed—sustained during fluvial transport; their lithologies reflect those of the rocks outcropping in Val Tartano. The finer fractions (gravels, sands, and silts) are mostly found just beneath this surface layer and within the voids between coarser clasts. In some sections (Photo 2), it is possible to observe the internal structure of the deposits, with heterogenous lenticular layering and imbricated pebbles stacked in the direction of the current.

Photo 2 – Section of the fan

In July 1987, heavy rainfall occurred in the Province of Sondrio and other areas, contributing to numerous flood and landslide events that caused fatalities and extensive damage. The Tartano fan was affected by a large debris flow associated with another reactivation of the Pizzo della Pruna landslide (Francani, 2017).

Debris flows are dense mixtures of water, fine materials, and rock debris that flow—sometimes very rapidly and often in successive surges—down slopes or through steep mountain streams. The liquid and solid phases travel at the same speed. Along their path, debris flows can entrain additional material—for example, from the streambed—thereby increasing in volume. These are highly hazardous phenomena that have been the subject of extensive research (see the short video at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xyfreVn-j2s>), and they can significantly contribute to the formation of fans. Sturdy reinforced concrete wedges—with their apex facing upstream and equipped with a metal covering—protect the piers of the SS38 Stelvio viaduct, which crosses the Tartano fan (Photo 3), from the material transported by the stream or by debris flows.

Photo 3 – The SS38 viaduct crossing the Tartano fan, with protective wedges for its piers

Walking eastward, one comes across a dirt path, one branch of which turns north and passes beneath the viaduct. Following this path leads to a section of the old SS38 highway, which was decommissioned and partially demolished after the 1987 flood (Fig. 3 and Photo 4). The former roadbed lies at a significantly lower elevation than the current viaduct, supported by a series of arches with smaller spans that were more easily obstructed by debris moving across the fan. From this site, one can also observe the town of Desco, the Adda River, the fractured rock masses of the Colmen di Dazio, the niche of a rockfall that has affected the relief even recently (a boulder is visible in the riverbed), and several stabilization measures such as rockfall netting and anchoring systems.

Photo 4 – The old SS38 and the new one

When arriving at or leaving the area of this first stop, in addition to other instability phenomena on the Colmen di Dazio, one can observe the fan formed by the Roncaiola, Malasca, and Ranciga streams, on which the town of Talamona is built (Fig. 3). The fan has a significant surface area,

volume, and slope, despite the fact that the contributing streams have relatively small drainage basins. This suggests that landslide phenomena occurring within those basins—and the materials they supply—play an important role in the formation of the fan itself (De Finis, 2016; Crosta & Frattini, 2004). Striking evidence of faults, fractures, and rockfalls can be seen on the slope upstream of Talamona (Photo 1).

2.2.2 Second stop: the “Punt de Sass” in Villa di Tirano

The second stop on the route is about 45 km from the previous one, in Central Valtellina. Less than twenty meters south of the SS38 and the railway, in the municipality of Villa di Tirano, one can spot the “Punt de Sass,” a beautiful stone bridge that rises almost mysteriously from the surrounding countryside (Fig. 4 and Photo 5).

Fig. 4 – The Ponte di Sasso and the surrounding area. 1) Location of the Ponte di Sasso (the structure is within the square); 2) Town of Villa di Tirano; 3) Adda River; 4) Poschiavino Stream; 5) Sanctuary of the Madonna di Tirano; 6) Town of Tirano. The red star in the inset at the top left shows the location of the area within the context of the Province of Sondrio

Photo 5 - The Ponte di Sasso seen from the southwest, on the opposite side of the SS28; in the background, Mount Masuccio

The structure is representative of the transformations in the Valtellina valley floor linked to changes in the course of the Adda River and is also classified as a geosite of the Province of Sondrio (Regione Lombardia and IREALP, 2008).

The bridge, which dates back at least to the late 15th century, is approximately 28 meters long and features two large symmetrical arches of about 12 meters, reinforced with iron keystones and separated by a central pier with nearly triangular buttresses and cutwaters on both sides. The terminal walls flare outward beyond the width of the bridge deck. The quality of its construction suggests the bridge held particular importance, though some portions appear more roughly built, indicating later modifications (Masa, 2014; Regione Lombardia and IREALP, 2008). A conservation-focused restoration was completed in 2000.

The valley floor where the structure stands—as confirmed by historical records—has been affected by repeated flooding and shifts in the course of the Adda River. The bridge fell permanently out of

use in 1817 after a flood diverted the river's course, which was followed by embankment works and the construction of a new bridge and road (Regione Lombardia and IREALP, 2008). Today, the *Punt de Sass* is located about 400 meters from the river.

From the bridge, looking northeast, one can see Mount Masuccio, which rises above the beautiful town of Tirano and stands at the confluence of the Valtellina and the Poschiavo Valley—traversed by the Poschiavino Stream and lying almost entirely within the Swiss canton of Graubünden.

The mountain is composed of rocks from the Austroalpine Domain, and its southern flank is affected by a phenomenon known as Deep-Seated Gravitational Slope Deformation (DSGSD), which appears as a massive landslide—with a bulging base—extending from near the summit all the way down to the Adda River (Photo 6). DSGSDs are large-scale slope movements that can involve entire mountainsides from ridge to valley floor (as in the case of Mount Masuccio), and can affect rock masses hundreds of meters thick. These movements develop through internal deformation of the rock mass and do not require a continuous slip surface or failure zone.

Typically, DSGSDs evolve slowly and imperceptibly (millimeters per year), causing limited damage. However, they can also include highly active zones that give rise to faster and more hazardous landslide processes such as rock avalanches, massive rockfalls, or other types of shallow to deep-seated failures. These are often favored by the abundance of surface debris and the poor mechanical properties of the rock masses. The DSGSD of Mount Masuccio, in particular, has experienced partial remobilizations, localized landslides, and erosion along the gullies that incise or border the slope, as well as slope failures at its base triggered by the erosive action of the Adda River (Agostoni et al., 1997).

From the *Punt de Sass*, one can also see, on the left bank of the Adda, the large Sernio fan, which is cut off at the river by a high erosion scarp (Photo 6).

Photo 6 – The DSGSD of Mount Masuccio and the Sernio fan as seen from the Ponte di Sasso site. 1) Detachment area; 2) Middle section; 3) Toe; 4) Profile of the Sernio fan with the terminal scarp facing the Adda River; 5) Sanctuary of the Madonna di Tirano

2.2.3 Third stop: the Sanctuary of the Madonna di Tirano

From Villa di Tirano, following the SS38, one reaches Tirano and enters Piazza della Basilica, located at the mouth of Val Poschiavo and crossed by the Tirano–Saint Moritz section of the Rhaetian Railway, which has been part of the UNESCO World Heritage Site since 2008.

Overlooking the square stands the magnificent Sanctuary of the Madonna di Tirano (Photos 7 and 8), whose construction began in 1505, was completed in 1528, and was later modified and finalized in its current form in 1703 (Regione Lombardia, 2014; Regione Lombardia and IREALP, 2008).

The Sanctuary holds great religious and artistic significance and is also part of the geological heritage of the Province of Sondrio due to its petrographic interest, related to the variety of stone materials used in its construction (Regione Lombardia and IREALP, 2008). Among these materials, particularly noteworthy are: the local white marble from the Pum quarry used for the portals, the dome, the bell tower balustrade, the pediments, and the sacristy; serpentinite used for the architrave on the façade; limestone from Arzo (Canton Ticino) used in the eight columns supporting the majestic wooden

organ; black limestone from Perledo-Varenna with polychrome inlays in the main altar; marble for statues and high-reliefs sourced from nearby quarries; and finally, the white, black, and red floor tiles, presumably made of marble, black limestone from Perledo-Varenna, Rosso Ammonitico Veronese limestone, and limestone from Arzo.

The Sanctuary, due to its features and location, is the point along the route where history, art, culture, geography, and geology come together most profoundly.

Photo 7 – The Sanctuary of the Madonna di Tirano, in the evening

Photo 8 – The monumental organ supported by eight columns and the polychrome floor

2.2.4 Fourth stop: the DSGSD of Mount Masuccio and the Sernio fan

The lower portion of the DSGSD of Mount Masuccio is bounded to the southwest by the small Valle di Canale and its namesake stream. This stream has formed, at the base of the slope, a rather large and steep fan that appears to be well fed by debris coming from the DSGSD, partially covering its toe (Fig. 5).

Following the road from Tirano toward the village of Baruffini, one first crosses the fan and then remains almost continuously on the bulging base of the DSGSD. This convex morphology—further highlighted by the vineyard terraces—is clearly visible when looking northeast from the fan itself (Fig. 5).

From Baruffini, on the left bank of the Adda River, one can see the village of Sernio and its large fan (Fig. 5 and Photo 9), which is visible throughout the area and was already noted from the Punt de Sass. To the northeast, along the river, lies the small reservoir of the Sernio dam, built in the 1930s (Fig. 5 and Photo 9). The reservoir corresponds to the terminal portion of a much larger lake that formed when the Adda was dammed by a landslide that fell from the base of Mount Masuccio in 1807. The lake, nearly 2.6 km long and over 1 km² in surface area, flooded part of the territory of Lovero (Angeloni, 2012 and Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 – The area with the DSGSD of Mount Masuccio and the Sernio fan includes: 1) the town of Tirano, 2) the Sanctuary of the Madonna di Tirano, 3) the Poschiavino Stream and the Swiss border, 4) Val Poschiavino, 5) the fan of the Valle di Canale stream (with its fan shape outlined by solid lines), 6) the body of the DSGSD of Mount Masuccio, 7) the village of Baruffini, 8) the Sernio Dam, 9) the village of Sernio, 10) the Sernio fan, 11) Valchiosa, 12) the Valle dello Stradello and the valley of the Refreddo stream, and 13) the village of Lovero

Photo 9 – The Sernio fan and Valchiosa seen from Baruffini

The detrital cover and the fractured rock mass of the DSGSD promote landslide development, both due to their reduced mechanical strength and because they facilitate deep infiltration and circulation of water; this water further decreases the strength of the materials and increases their weight.

According to contemporary accounts, the 1807 landslide occurred on December 8th after an exceptionally rainy autumn. In the days immediately preceding the event, smaller collapses of increasing size and intensity were reported, mostly concentrated at the toe of the landslide area, where stress and deformation are typically greatest (Angeloni, 2012). The material that failed on December 8th fell into the Adda riverbed, damming the river, and climbed up the left bank, reaching the scarp of the Sernio fan, where it accumulated mostly at the base. The mass, composed primarily of large rock blocks, offered significant resistance to erosion and to the hydraulic pressures exerted by infiltrating water, the lake forming upstream, and the water expected to flow over the deposit once

the overflow level was reached. Thus, a sudden collapse of the landslide dam—potentially causing a catastrophic flood of Tirano with both water and debris—did not appear likely (Angeloni, 2012).

The main concern at the time was the possibility of additional material detaching from the landslide's headscarp, which could fall onto the dam where work was underway to manage water outflow, or into the forming lake, generating anomalous waves (*ibid.*). The consulted literature does not report any significant events in this regard.

The large Sernio fan is also part of a history involving landslides and lakes. The fan (Fig. 5 and Photo 9) extends northwestward on the left bank of the Adda from the mouths of Valchiosa, Valle dello Stradello, and the valley of the Refreddo Stream, all incised into rocks of the Austroalpine Domain. De Finis and Bini (2014), building on earlier research, classify fans like that of Sernio as landslide-dominated fans. These fans are primarily composed of landslide material sourced from the contributing upstream catchments and are characterized by:

1. a very large surface area compared to that of the drainage basin;
2. apical portions extending into the upstream valleys;
3. a relatively steep slope;
4. source basins bordered entirely or largely by a landslide headscarp;
5. smooth and regular topographic surfaces;
6. ephemeral streams with very limited discharge;
7. steep and high scarps at the toe, caused by erosion from the main valley's watercourse.

According to the conceptual model proposed in De Finis (2016), landslide-dominated fans form as a result of rock avalanches that occur in the source basins and subsequently evolve into debris avalanches. Rock avalanches often originate from other types of landslides, such as rotational slides or rock mass detachments, and involve large volumes of debris (more than 500,000–1,000,000 m³) that move in a fluid-like manner, reaching very high speeds (up to 100 m/s). Along their path, they may incorporate additional material—especially if water-saturated—leading to an increase in volume and transformation into debris avalanches, which are fast-moving flows of mixed materials.

In the formation of a landslide-dominated fan, the moving mass is initially confined within a valley, which it rapidly traverses before spreading out in a fan shape at the valley outlet, reaching the opposite valley wall, extending upstream and downstream, and damming the main watercourse, thereby forming a lake. Erosion of the deposit by the same river produces steep, high scarps at the fan's toe, while the smooth surface of the fan is interpreted as the result of successive debris flows that, over time, reshape and cover the original landslide deposit, concealing its irregularities (Jarman, 2011).

The source basins of landslide-dominated fans are typically affected by DSGSDs, crossed by major structural lineaments (such as regional faults), and composed of rocks with particular structural features—like mylonites—associated with zones of intense deformation (De Finis & Bini, 2014). The high degree of fracturing in the rock mass, combined with the presence of discontinuities and possibly DSGSDs, favors the occurrence of rock avalanches. One such example can be seen in the short YouTube video at <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/SK38UDPhQEK>; note the significant change in slope morphology following the collapse.

The characteristics of Valchiosa and the Sernio fan are consistent with this framework (De Finis et al., 2015). The head of the valley is marked by a high, steep scarp with an arcuate morphology typical of landslide headscarps, and it shows highly fractured rock masses, a major joint system inclined at 65° toward the slope, and clear evidence of DSGSD. In contrast, there are no signs of glacial erosion, such as striated or polished bedrock surfaces (*roches moutonnées*). Glacial deposits are found only in a narrow zone upstream of the upper scarp and are absent from the rest of the basin. This supports the interpretation of Valchiosa as a valley formed after the last glaciation (De Finis et al., 2015).

Borehole investigations conducted upstream of the Sernio fan have revealed, over several kilometers and at various depths, layers of silt and clay indicative of former lake basins and multiple damming episodes (De Finis et al., 2015).

The terminal scarps of the fan—high, steep, and extensive—are the result of erosion by the Adda River and are affected by evident instability phenomena. The deposits exposed along these scarps,

based on their characteristics, are attributed to repeated debris flows that partially eroded earlier deposits (De Finis et al., 2015; De Finis, 2016).

The combination of features in the area suggests that the main event responsible for the formation of Valchiosa and the Sernio fan was the sliding, along the previously mentioned joints, of an enormous volume of rock mass, followed by its transformation into a rock avalanche/debris avalanche and the formation of the fan. This fan then dammed the Adda River, giving rise to a lake. Subsequent debris flows gradually covered the landslide mass and smoothed the topography, creating the gentle landscape of the broad agricultural plain around Sernio, which is now largely cultivated with apple orchards. These debris flows were fed by material from the main event and by debris produced through the progressive dismantling of the rocks in Valchiosa.

The volume involved in the initial collapse and the current volume of the fan can be estimated—albeit with considerable uncertainty—at up to one billion cubic meters and around 500 million cubic meters, respectively (De Finis et al., 2015).

The erosive action of the Adda carved through the ancient natural dam, leading to the drainage of the lake, and contributed—together with slope instability processes—to shaping the scarps of the fan. These scarps, even today, are subject to landslides and can be eroded at their base by the river during major flood events.

2.2.5 Fifth stop: the Val Pola landslide and the Aquilone memorial

Continuing from Tirano toward Bormio, the SS38 ascends, crosses, and descends the Sernio fan and shortly thereafter enters Upper Valtellina. Taking the “Le Prese” exit and following the SP27 near Sondalo, one passes through a section of the valley with a north–south orientation, shaped by a fault system dating back to the final phase of the Alpine orogeny.

After a few kilometers, massive check dams can be seen along the course of the Adda River, and shortly thereafter one comes face-to-face with the Val Pola landslide (Fig. 6 and Photo 10), listed among the geosites of the Province of Sondrio (Regione Lombardia and IREALP, 2008). From a

turnout along the SP27, a small paved road leads to a viewing area (marked with a P in Fig. 6), which offers a good vantage point.

Fig. 6 – The Val Pola area. 1) Check dams on the Adda River; 2) Landslide detachment surface; 3) Landslide detachment surface; 4) Scarp at the head of the landslide area predating the 1987 event; 5) Embankment; 6) Village of Aquilone. The dashed line indicates the route leading to the SP27 and to the viewpoint marked as P in the text. The coordinates of the viewpoint are Lat: 46°22'51.99"N, Long: 10°21'29.10"E

Photo 10 – The landslide and the area at its toe, seen from viewpoint P. Note the debris lobes formed at the toe of the landslide, the containment embankment, and the tree vegetation—predominantly larch—with individuals of roughly the same age, which grew after the event

In mid-July 1987, the Central Alps experienced exceptional rainfall accompanied by high temperatures. Between July 15 and 22, more than 600 mm of rain fell—about half of Valtellina’s annual average. The 0°C isotherm remained between 3,500 and 4,000 meters in elevation, causing the melting of snow cover and intense, concentrated runoff on glaciers. This extreme meteorological scenario led to water saturation of slopes and increased surface and channel runoff, resulting in severe flooding and hundreds of landslides (Crosta, 2004; Crosta, 2010; Angeloni, 2011).

The Val Pola landslide, which detached from the eastern slope of Mount Zandila, was the largest event and had the most severe consequences during that dramatic period. An excellent article in the *Bollettino Storico Alta Valtellina* (Angeloni, 2011) describes what occurred from both geological and

human perspectives and includes a rich photographic archive; additional images are available on the dedicated pages of Arpa Lombardia listed in the references.

The eastern flank of Mount Zandila consists mainly of magmatic and metamorphic rocks belonging to the Austroalpine Domain. The Val Pola landslide was a reactivation of an ancient landslide located at the intersection of two fracture systems inclined at approximately 45° and 90° toward the Adda valley. The landslide extended over a vertical drop of 700 meters, between elevations of 2,350 and 1,650 meters above sea level, and had a headscarp defined by a continuous scarp about 700 meters long and up to 100 meters high, laterally bounded by two subvertical fractures trending east–west (Agostoni et al., 1997; Crosta, 2010; Angeloni, 2011, especially Fig. 22).

Val Pola, deeply incised by the stream of the same name, developed on the left side of the landslide. The intense and sustained rainfall of July 18 and 19, 1987, triggered numerous shallow rockfalls from the valley flanks, stream overflows, and debris flows. These debris flows formed a large fan at the mouth of Val Pola, which dammed the Adda River and created a lake with a volume of 50,000 m³ and a depth ranging from 1 to 5 meters (Crosta, 2010).

On July 25, a 600-meter-long fracture was detected at the base of the paleolandslide scarp; it progressively extended to a length of 900 meters and evolved into a visible scarp (Crosta, 2004). An alert was issued, and monitoring of the phenomenon began using the available resources. The settlements of Sant’Antonio Morignone, Morignone, Poz, and Tirindrè were evacuated, along with the locality of San Martino di Serravalle, located at the foot of the slope opposite Mount Zandila. The hamlet of Aquilone, farther north, was considered to be at a sufficient distance not to be directly affected by the landslide, and the evacuation initially planned for it was revoked (Agostoni, 2011).

On July 28 at 7:23 AM, a massive wedge of rock—approximately 34 million cubic meters—slid down the slope along the detachment surfaces labeled 2 and 3 in Fig. 6, corresponding to discontinuities in the rock mass. The landslide initially moved along surface 2 toward the northeast, transversely across the slope and in the direction of the Pola Stream; after impacting a rocky spur

north of the stream, it abruptly changed direction and transformed into a rock avalanche (Crosta, 2010).

This avalanche rushed toward the valley floor at estimated speeds between 50 and 108 m/s (180–390 km/h), entraining an additional 5–8 million cubic meters of debris along its path and expanding by approximately 30% during deposition (*ibid.*). The landslide surged 300 meters up the opposite slope, burying San Martino di Serravalle, and propagated 1.5 km downstream and 1 km upstream (Crosta, 2010; Agostoni et al., 1997). Upstream, the impact of the material with valley-floor alluvium and the previously mentioned lake generated a wave of mud and debris up to 95 meters high, preceded by a violent air blast. The wave, still 15–20 meters high at a distance of approximately 1.3 km, traveled a total of 2.7 km, reaching the hamlet of Aquilone, destroying several houses and killing twenty-one people. Seven workers engaged in restoring communications between Sondalo and Bormio were also killed (Angeloni, 2011). Sant'Antonio Morignone, Morignone, Poz, and Tirindrè were completely destroyed.

The landslide deposit formed a new dam across the Adda River, creating another lake, which reached a maximum surface area of 760,000 m² (Agostoni et al., 1997). A collapse of the dam or the fall of unstable blocks from the left side of the landslide slope into the lake could have triggered destructive waves threatening downstream settlements. To mitigate the risk, several pumping stations were installed to control the lake's growth and manage potential Adda floodwaters, and two bypass tunnels were constructed through the landslide deposit to permanently drain the lake (Agostoni, 2011).

Between August 23 and 26, new and intense rainfall caused the lake level to rise rapidly, making it necessary to issue evacuation orders for numerous downstream settlements. On August 27, it was decided to suspend ongoing work and proceed with a controlled overflow of the lake. This operation involved releasing water downstream by adding flow upstream from the Adda River using discharges from the Cancano Dam, managed by the Milan Electric Company (AEM, now A2A). The intervention was preceded by the excavation of a drainage channel and the lowering of the overflow threshold. The entire operation was monitored by Civil Protection authorities to study the behavior of the

landslide mass and to prevent dangerous collapses of the dam due to the pressure of water infiltrating it. The controlled overflow was completed on September 1 (Agostoni, 2011).

The final stabilization of the area included several main components. On the right bank of the river, the landslide deposit was reshaped to create an embankment aimed at containing debris washed out from the landslide area and preventing the gradual infilling of downstream structures (Agostoni, 2011 and Photo 10). Along the Adda River, multiple check dams were constructed to reduce sediment transport and minimize fluvial erosion. On the left bank, the deposit was reworked into terraces reinforced with metal frameworks, and the road network was restored. The bypass tunnels are still in place.

It is worth noting the gradual recolonization of the area by vegetation—particularly the establishment of forests dominated by larch trees, with individuals of roughly the same age—which have colonized the debris lobes at the landslide toe and the zones originally buried by the deposit, including those on the left bank (Fig. 6 and Photo 10). One can imagine that, over time, forest growth will increasingly cover the slope, partially concealing the traces of this major geological event. However, the morphological imprint of the landslide will persist for a long time and, as in many other Alpine areas and mountain chains worldwide, will remain both a testimony and a warning of what occurred.

Continuing toward Aquilone, one crosses a section of the valley floor shaped partly by the landslide deposits and reaches the Memorial to the Victims (Photo 11). Inaugurated in 2007, the Memorial is a collective expression of grief, remembrance, resilience, and solidarity. The victims are not remembered through an impersonal list of names, but through their photographs, displayed on a block of stone placed just to the left of the small chapel. Inside the chapel, a fresco commemorates the event, while images on the eastern outer wall narrate the sequence of events. In the peaceful green space of the Memorial stands the old Aquilone fountain, which survived the destructive wave, was damaged during post-landslide reconstruction works, and was later restored (Agostoni, 2011).

Photo 11 – The Val Pola Landslide Victims Memorial

According to Matteo Sambrizzi and Stefano Confortola, two local residents and witnesses of the 1987 events, the fountain represents an object of memory which, following a sudden and dramatic event capable of erasing everyday life, preserves a part of oneself and one's past, helping to reconnect with the new reality. The structure above all embodies the sacrifice of mountain people: carved from a single block of stone, it was crafted with effort and skill by local stonemasons and was once used to water livestock. Having survived the disaster, it has become a symbol of resilience and continuity. Its new placement allowed the community to come together twenty years after the landslide and to “refresh themselves in memory” during a moment of collective remembrance (Angeloni 2011).

2.2.6 Sixth stop: Verzedo and the mouth of the Val di Rezzalo

Returning from the Memorial toward Morbegno along the SP27, one reaches the locality of Verzedo, from which it is possible to observe—on the left bank of the Adda River—the lower portion of a small valley that features, at its mouth, a steep debris cone incised by the river (Fig. 7). These landforms appear to be the result, on a smaller scale, of landslide processes partially similar to those that likely gave rise to Valchiosa and the Sernio fan.

Fig. 8 – The Verzedo area. 1) Check dams along the Adda River downstream of the Val Pola landslide, also visible in Fig. 6; 2) Verzedo locality; 3) Debris cone; 4) Detachment niche. In the inset, the mouth of the small valley is shown as photographed from the SP27. The course of the Adda River, marked with number 5, is barely visible through the vegetation. Note the additional landforms along the slope described in the text

Just to the north and south, additional landforms can be observed that may be interpreted as detachment niches and other debris accumulations at the base of the slope. The detrital deposits are incised by small streams and, as suggested by the unvegetated areas, are likely still partially active due to falling blocks and minor rock collapses from the overlying cliffs. Farther south, the slope is

deeply cut by a narrow gully, which features a steep fan at its outlet. The formation of this fan is attributed to landslide processes and sediment transport.

The instability phenomena appear to be closely linked to the presence of discontinuities within the rock masses.

Continuing along the road for about 3 km past Verzedo, one reaches the locality of Grailè, which offers a beautiful view of the mouth of the Val di Rezzalo (Fig. 9 and Photo 12). The valley lies on the left bank of the Adda River, is traversed by the Rezzalasco Stream, and is set within rocks of the Austroalpine Domain.

Fig. 9 – The area at the mouth of the Val di Rezzalo. 1) Adda River; 2) Fan of the Rezzalasco Stream and the stream itself; 3) Entrance to the locality of Grailè, from which Photo 12 was taken (coordinates: Lat: 46°20'37.84"N, Long: 10°21'1.62"E); 4) The locality of Grailè; 5) The village of Frontale; 6) The DSGSD between Val di Rezzalo and Valle Scala; 7) Landslide area; 8) Val di Rezzalo; 9) Valle Scala

Photo 12 – The fan of the Rezzalasco Stream and the mouth of the Val di Rezzalo. The numbers correspond to those in Fig. 9. 2) Fan of the Rezzalasco Stream and the stream itself; 5) The village of Frontale; 6) The DSGSD between Val di Rezzalo and Valle Scala; 7) Landslide area

In the foreground, the Rezzalasco fan is visible. The characteristics of the fan indicate that its formation was significantly influenced by both debris flow deposits originating from Val di Rezzalo and materials detached from the landslide area at the mouth of the valley, which will be discussed shortly. As in other cases, the Adda River is pushed toward the opposite slope, suggesting that the fan has undergone phases of rapid growth in relatively recent times (Chiesa et al., 2011).

To the north, on the right bank of the Rezzalasco Stream, lies the morphological terrace with the village of Frontale, situated on the southwestern slope of Corno di Boero, which is affected by DSGSD phenomena. Further inside Val di Rezzalo, a large and clearly visible landslide area can be observed (Photos 12 and 13).

Rockfalls are the predominant type of instability and are continually evolving due to the high degree of fracturing in the rock masses and the intense fragmentation processes caused by freeze–thaw cycles (cryoclastism). Rainfall and erosion by the Rezzalasco Stream at the base of the slope also contribute to destabilizing portions of the rock mass. Above the scarps, moraine deposits are affected by

translational landslides and widespread solifluction processes—a slow movement of water-saturated surface deposits (Agostoni et al., 1997).

To the east, finally, on the slope between the mouths of Val di Rezzalo and Valle Scala, another DSGSD can be seen, consisting of a large rock wedge that has detached from the main ridge and is marked by prominent fractures (Fig. 9 and Photo 12).

Photo 13 – The landslide area at the mouth of Val di Rezzalo, crossed at the top by the road leading into the valley (the church and houses visible in the photo belong to the locality of Fumero)

2.2.7 Seventh and final stop: the fan of the Migiondo Stream

Continuing along the SP37 and reaching the area of Sondalo, one must leave the car and take—on the left bank of the Adda—the Sentiero Valtellina, a beautiful 114 km cycling and walking path that starts from the northern tip of Lake Como, in Colico, and leads all the way to Bormio. Walking downstream along the trail, one begins to notice, on the right, the high scarps at the base of the

Migiondo Stream fan, on which part of the town of Sondalo and the hamlets of Sommacologna and Migiondo are built.

The fan stretches for about 1.3 km into the upstream valley, covers an area of 1.2 km², and extends parallel to the Adda from Sondalo to just beyond Migiondo.

The best view of its scarps is at the confluence of the stream with the Adda, where the valley walls reach a height of around 100 meters (Fig. 10 and Photo 14).

Fig. 10 – The Migiondo Stream alluvial fan. 1) Migiondo Stream; 2) Village of Sommacologna; 3) Fan; 4) Boundary of the landslide deposit originating from Val Migiondo; 5) Village of Migiondo; 6) Town of Sondalo; 7) Area occupied by the lake. Photo 14 was taken approximately from point P. The boundaries of the landslide areas and the lake basin are approximate and based on Angeloni (2009)

The origin of the Migiondo fan, as in the case of Sernio, can be traced back to a rock avalanche, whose deposit was later covered by debris flows (Guglielmin and Orombelli, 2001). The materials at the base of the scarp—containing chaotically arranged rock blocks, some up to several meters in size—can indeed be attributed to such a rock avalanche. Above these, deposits showing rough stratification developed, which are consistent with subsequent debris flows. Some boulders appear to

protect the underlying sediments from surface runoff, causing erosion channels to preferentially form alongside the boulders themselves (Photo 14).

The Migiondo fan also extends to the right bank of the Adda River (Angeloni, 2009 and Fig. 10), and it undoubtedly dammed the river, raising the valley floor and leading to the formation of an upstream lake. Over time, the Adda eroded this natural dam, forming the present-day scarps, while the stream gradually adjusted to the river level by carving a deep gorge.

Borehole investigations in the area confirmed the presence of both landslide deposits and lacustrine basin sediments, indicating that the former lake extended as far as the Lenasco Stream fan, just upstream of Sondalo. The lake likely covered an area of about 0.7 km² and reached a maximum depth of 30 meters (Guglielmin and Orombelli, 2001; Dei Cas, 2002; Angeloni, 2012).

Photo 14 – The scarps of the Migiondo Stream fan. 1) Gorge at the stream’s confluence with the Adda River; 2) Deposits at the base of the scarp interpreted as the accumulation from a rock avalanche

At the head of Val Migiondo lies the ridge between Monte Fo and Passo del Gatto, from which the landslide that gave rise to the Migiondo Stream fan likely detached. Based on radiometric dating of

the lake deposits, the event can be traced back to approximately **8,700 years ago**, well after the retreat of the glaciers from the last glacial period (Guglielmin and Orombelli, 2001; Dei Cas, 2022).

It is interesting to note that local accounts and documents tell of a landslide originating from Monte Fo and the existence of a lake in Sondalo, dating the latter to the 5th or 12th century AD; however, there is no geological evidence supporting the existence of such a lake (Dei Cas, 2022).

2.2.8 Toward Morbegno: the Rhon fan

From Sondalo, following the SP37, one reaches Grosio and can rejoin the SS38. Heading back toward Morbegno, just before reaching Sondrio, the road climbs, branches off toward Chiuro and Ponte in Valtellina, and follows a long, gentle curve that crosses the locality of Casacce before descending again (Fig. 11). Here, one is on the large fan of the Rhon Stream, which—like those of Sernio and Migiondo—is also landslide-dominated (De Finis and Bini, 2014).

Note in Fig. 11 the steep slope and large size of the fan compared to that of the Val di Rhon, as well as the instability phenomena at the head of the valley. For comparison, the village of Chiuro lies on a much smaller fan formed at the mouth of a significantly larger valley, Valfontana, than the Val di Rhon.

Fig. 11 - The fan of the Rhon Stream. 1) Adda River; 2) Village of Chiuro; 3) Fan; 4) Village of Ponte in Valtellina; 5) Val di Rhon; 6) Valfontana, crossed by the stream of the same name

3. A final reflection

The excursion described in this contribution passes through areas of the Valtellina valley floor that have been affected—even in recent times—by high-intensity geological events. However, phenomena such as debris flows and landslides, even when not extreme, represent significant hazard factors. Hazard becomes actual risk when vulnerable elements—such as people, homes and settlements, infrastructure, and agricultural or industrial areas—are present, especially in a setting where the majority of the Valtellina population resides.

The visit will typically take place under stable weather and geological conditions, but it is important to remember that the landforms observed, even when they are evidence of past events, also serve as a warning for the future.

4. Notes on the route

All the locations visited during the excursion are accessible by car, but they can also be reached—possibly over multiple days—via the Sentiero Valtellina. The hamlet of Baruffini is farther from the trail, but the Sernio fan and an oblique view of Valchiosa can still be observed from the Valle di Canale fan. From Tirano, one can also easily reach Lake Poschiavo, which was formed by the damming of the Poschiavino Stream by a landslide deposit that is still clearly visible today (for a description of the area, see for example Angeloni, 2012).

Visiting the Tartano fan may be difficult or impossible for individuals with limited mobility, but the area—and the Pizzo della Pruna landslide—can be clearly seen from the hamlet of Desco, which is accessible from Morbegno.

Finally, the school excursion lasts one day, and for this reason it can only briefly touch on the many historical, artistic, and industrial archaeological features along the route—from vineyard terraces to churches, historic buildings, castles, and hydroelectric plants. With more time, however, the observation of geology can become the starting point for a broader exploration of the Valtellina valley floor and surrounding areas. A good place to begin is the Tourism Service website of the Provincial Administration: <https://www.valtellina.it>.

Photographic material

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